

Food Selection and Consumption Practices of Diabetic Patients in Nsukka Metropolis of Enugu State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study sought to find out the food selection and consumption practices of diabetic patients in Nsukka Metropolis. Three research questions guided the study. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population for the study was 520 consisting of 204 registered diabetic patients in Bishop Shanahan hospital and 316 registered diabetic patients in University of Nigeria medical center, Nsukka. Purposive sampling technique was used to select 102 patients consisting of 45 in Bishop Shanahan hospital and 57 diabetic patients in University of Nigeria medical center, Nsukka. Structured questionnaires were used for data collection. Data were analyzed using frequency, percentages, mean and standard deviation to answer all the research questions. The study revealed that the foods selected for consumption mostly by diabetics are Bambara nut pudding (46.4%), Semovita (45.4%) / Garri (54.6%) / Wheat (42.3%) with assorted soups, Rice alone (48.5%), beans alone (53.6%), rice and beans together (61.9%), bean cake with pap (43.3%), moi-moi with pap (47.4%), bread and beverages, yam and beans. The food consumption practices of diabetic patients in Nsukka metropolis revealed that; 67% of Diabetic patients skipped meals occasionally, while 71.1% of Diabetic patients occasionally eat more than necessary. 67.0% of Diabetic patients occasionally eat high fat foods like fried protein foods like beef and eggs. Factors that influence food selection and consumption practices of Diabetics in Nsukka Metropolis are difficulty in avoiding favorite foods (3.17) and this practice makes diabetic patients to consume unhealthy foods. 60.8% mention the economy as contributing to reduce the options of what to eat, difficulty in departing from regular meals consumed over time (3.25) makes avoiding certain foods difficult, continuous need to be conscious with food eaten (3.07) makes managing diabetes a complicated issue. In conclusion, Diabetes is a serious health condition that kills easily if not managed. The study recommended on the need for creating awareness by hospitals/health personnel on the right foods to eat access to affordable foods and regular medical check. Home Economists should develop an affordable diabetic diet across all the socio-economic levels

Keywords: Diabetes, Food Consumption, Patients; Diet; Health.

Introduction

Diabetes is one of the chronic diseases that affect both the young and old in the society although it typically affects the old more. According to World Health Organization (2019), at least 422 million people worldwide suffer from diabetes. In developing countries, especially in Africa, increase in diabetes prevalence is expected to occur. American Diabetes Association

(2014) This increase in incidence of diabetes in developing countries follows the trend of urbanization and lifestyle changes perhaps most importantly a "Western - Style" diet World Health Organization (2019).

In Nigeria, though no estimate of the individuals suffering from diabetes has been made, there has been alarming cases of diabetes various locations in Nigeria. (Ogbera & Ekpebegh, 2014). In a pre-study

visit to All Saints hospital Nsukka, revealed that in a recent diabetes screening, out of 205 that attended, 65 percent were diabetic. Also, at the Bishop Shanahan hospital, the number of patients that attend the weekly diabetic clinic is alarming. Diabetes leads to hyperglycemia, which can lead to acute and chronic complications such as diabetic ketoacidosis, coronary artery disease, cerebrovascular disease, kidney and eye diseases, disorders of the nerves, among others. To avoid these complications, it has been established that diabetic patient should watch their food intake especially carbohydrate intake.

Food supply and intake is very important to the body regardless of age, sex, religion, occupation, or season. Food must be taken with consciousness for well-being of the body. Too much or too little food intakes may cause serious damage to the body system. Diabetes is one of the chronic diseases that affect both the young and old in Nigerian society. According to Adebisi Adebisi, (2013), Diabetes mellitus is a state that begins when the pancreas stops working completely, the insulin production or the produced insulin is not efficient in the body. In that case, the cells do not get the food necessary for their life. It is a chronic disease that lasts for many years. Diabetes is a disorder of carbohydrates metabolism characterized by high blood sugar level (hyperglycemic) and high level of sugar in urine (glycosuria). According to Oladapo, Jude-Ojei, Koleosho, & Roland-Ayodele (2013), it is accompanied in many cases by secondary alteration of fat and protein metabolism resulting in an array of physical disorder.

Diabetes has been recognized as a devastating and a deadly disease for over 2000 years Agbabiaka, (2010). In 1922, Fredrick Banting and his assistant Charles Best discovered insulin to save the lives of diabetic patients. It has reached the level of great public concern as over four million people are suffering this ailment and only 20 percent of this group is aware of their status (Adem, Gebremariam & Gelaw, 2015). The prevalence of DM in adults have been related to unfavorable trends in factors such

as overweight and sedentary habits as demonstrated in longitudinal, ecological and migration studies (Micha, Peñalvo, Cudhea, Imamura, Rehm, & Mozaffarian, 2017). According to Micha et al (2017), DM can also be triggered by interaction between environmental and genetic factors when individuals become exposed to an obesogenic environment. Since insulin discovery, medical breakthrough continues to ease the sufferings and prolong the life of people with diabetes. There are three types of diabetes, Insulin sensitive (type 1) and Insulin insensitive (type II) and intestinal diabetes (Chinenye, 2015).

Type I diabetes (Insulin Independent Diabetes Mellitus (IDDM) is the leading chronic disease among children and young adult (30). Agbabiaka (2010) reported that it sometimes starts from birth. In type 1 diabetes, the person's immune system attacks the system cells of the pancreas that normally synthesis the hormone insulin. Soon the pancreas can no longer produce insulin and after each meal, blood glucose remains elevated. Type 2 Diabetes (Non-Insulin Depended Diabetes Mellitus (NIDDM) is because of insulin resistance of the body cells which may be combined with relatively reduced insulin secretion, it is the most common type. The pancreas becomes less able to produce insulin. People with type 2 Diabetes must take insulin to supplement their own insulin. This type 2 Diabetes occurs particularly in people that are 35 years and above. Type 2 Diabetes also increases with age. Gestational Diabetes is a form of diabetes that is diagnosed only during pregnancy. It occurs in African women who are obese or have a family history of type-2 diabetes. It requires treatment to bring the maternal blood glucose to normal levels and avoid complications of pregnancy wastage and other complications in the baby. As a result of the body system of diabetic patients, they have to pay special interest to their food intake which requires the diabetic patients to have adequate dietary knowledge.

Dietary knowledge is a significant factor towards the improvement of the dietary pattern in the society. According to Lesser, Gasevic & Lear, (2014) knowledge regarding

diet can change the unfavorable dietary pattern among the diabetic patients. Wang, Song, Ba, Zhu & Wen (2014) indicates that proper practices according to recommended diet prevents further complications of diabetes. It is estimated by World Health Organization (2019) that there is the association between dietary pattern and mortality rate. Dietary knowledge is important in regulating the food intake practices of diabetic patients. For instance, type 2 diabetes mellitus requires the adoption and maintenance of multiple self-care behaviors to achieve and sustain glycemic control, (Sullivan, & Joseph, 2008). These behaviors include monitoring blood glucose, exercising regularly, and adhering to a recommended eating regimen. Groop, & Tuomi, (2013). showed that people with diabetes found the most difficult component of their self-care regimen to be adhering to a healthful diet. Sullivan and Joseph (2008) posited that people with diabetes were reported to be resistant to dietary change when compared to people with other chronic diseases. Food selection and eating patterns are influenced by psychosocial, behavioral, and environmental elements.

To effectively modify dietary patterns among people with diabetes, it is important to identify the elements that influence food choices and eating behaviors. Although it is commonly known that diabetic patients should eat less of carbohydrates and more of protein, no previous study carried out in Nsukka shows if the diabetic patients adhere to it or not. Furthermore, a pre-study visits to All Saints hospital, it was showed that out of 205 that attended clinic, 65 percent were diabetic. Non- adherence of diabetic patients to recommended foods could lead to hypertension, cardiovascular issues, and obesity, it became necessary to ascertain the food Selection and Consumption practices of diabetic patients in Nsukka Metropolis.

Objectives of the Study

The major objective of the study was to ascertain food selection and consumption practices of diabetic patients in Nsukka Metropolis. Specifically, the study sought to ascertain the:-

1. Foods selection by diabetic patients for consumption in Nsukka metropolis.
2. Food consumption practices of diabetic patients in Nsukka metropolis.
3. Factors that influence food selection and consumption practices of diabetic patients in Nsukka metropolis.

Methodology

Design of the study

The study adopted a descriptive survey design.

Area of the study

The study was conducted in Nsukka metropolis. Nsukka is a town and Local Government Area in southeast Nigeria in Enugu State with an area of 1,810 km² and a population of 309,633, (NPC) ,2002). Currently, the town has a good number of diabetic patients that visit hospitals such as University of Nigeria medical center, Nsukka, District Hospital Nsukka, Bishop Shanahan hospital and Faith Foundation Mission *Hospital Nsukka for medical care*.

Population for the study

The population for the study was 520 diabetic patients consisting of 204 registered type 1 and type 2 diabetic patients in Bishop Shanahan hospital and 316 registered diabetic patients in University of Nigeria medical center, Nsukka. (Bishop Shanahan hospital and University of Nigeria medical center, Nsukka outpatient's department ,2020)

Sample and sampling Technique

Purposive sampling technique was used to select 102 patients consisting of 45 in Bishop Shanahan hospital and 57 diabetic patients in University of Nigeria medical center, Nsukka. The criteria for judgment were that only diabetic patients that have been diagnosed with diabetes for up to five years were chosen since they are expected to have more experience on what to eat and what not to eat.

Method of data collection

The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire designed by the researchers based on extensive literature review. The draft questionnaire was subjected to face and content validation by three experts from the department of Home Economics University of Nigeria Nsukka. The final copy of the Questionnaire was structured into three sections: sections 1, 2 and 3. Section 1 and 2 has items with a 3-point response options ranging from 2 to 0 (Always = 2, Occasionally = 1&Never = 0). Section 3 have items with a 4-point rating scale, (Strongly Agree, SA = 4; Agree, A = 3; Disagree, D = 3; and strongly Disagree, SA = 1). 97 copies of the questionnaire were correctly completed representing a 95% return rate.

Method of Data Analysis

Data collected were analyzed using simple

percentages for the research questions 1and 2. While mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions 3. The mean score of 2.50 and above were regarded as "Agreed," while mean scores below 2.50 were "Disagreed".

Results

In Table 1, it was revealed that Bambara nut pudding and Garri were eaten very often by most of the diabetic patients because these items had the highest frequency and percentage of 46.4% and 54% respectively. Foo foo with different soups ogbono, egusi, and vegetable soups and ayarayaoka, were rarely eaten by most of the patients because these items had the highest frequency and percentage falling in the category of 'Never'. Fifteen items were eaten occasionally by a majority because these items had their highest frequency and percentage falling in the category of 'Occasionally'.

Table 1: Frequency Distribution and Percentages of the Most consumed Foods a by Diabetic patients in Nsukka Metropolis

S/N	FOODS	A (F)	O (F)	N (F)	A (%)	O (%)	N (%)	Remarks
1	Rice alone	22	48	28	22.7	48.5	28.8	O
2	Beans alone	22	52	23	19.6	53.6	18.6	O
3	Rice and beans together	19	60	18	19.6	61.9	18.6	O
4	Bean cake	33	53	11	34.0	54.6	11.3	O
5	Bean cake with pap	26	42	29	26.8	43.3	29.9	O
6	Moi-moi with pap	19	46	32	19.6	47.4	33.0	O
7	Semovita with ogbono	16	44	37	16.5	45.4	38.1	O
8	Semovita with egusi	21	51	25	21.6	52.6	25.8	O
9	Wheat with ogbono	40	41	16	41.2	42.3	16.5	O
10	Wheat with egusi	37	35	25	38.1	36.1	25.8	A
11	Foo foo with ogbono	24	30	43	24.7	30.9	44.4	N
12	Foo foo with egusi	23	32	42	23.7	33.0	43.3	N
13	Corn casserole (Ayarayaoka)	29	29	39	29.9	29.9	40.1	N
14	Bread and cocoa beverages	14	49	34	14.4	50.5	35.1	O
15	Bread and lipton	26	38	33	26.8	39.2	34.0	O
16	Yam and beans	21	55	21	21.6	56.7	21.6	O
17	Beans and bread	31	35	33	32.0	34.0	34.0	O
18	Bambara nut pudding (Okpa)	45	30	22	46.4	30.9	22.7	A
19	GarriEba with vegetable soup	53	26	18	54.6	26.8	18.6	A
20	Foo foo with vegetable soup	25	35	37	25.8	36.1	38.1	N
21	Moi-moi and garri	22	38	37	22.7	39.2	38.1	O

In Table 2, it was revealed that two items, 4 & 5 indicating (56.7%) and (62.9%) are highly practiced food consumption practices. Two items 8 & 9 (54.6 %) and (60.8%) were rarely practiced The remaining seven items were

practiced occasionally falling in the category of 'Occasionally' with frequency percentages ranging from 71.1% and 52.1% respectively.

Table 2: Frequency Distribution and Percentage of Food Consumption Practices of Diabetic Patients in Nsukka Metropolis

S/N	FOODS	A (F)	O (F)	N (F)	A (%)	O (%)	N (%)	Remarks
1	Skip meals in a day	16	65	16	16.5	67.0	16.5	O
2	Eat more than you know you should	16	69	12	16.5	71.1	12.4	O
3	Eat high fat foods like fried animal protein such as beef	23	65	9	23.7	67.0	9.0	O
4	Able to fit dietary management into your life in a positive manner	55	39	3	56.7	40.2	3.1	A
5	Involve family in helping you follow a meal plan	61	24	12	62.9	24.7	12.4	A
6	Eat only that which is available or affordable irrespective of content	28	59	10	22.7	53.6	23.7	O
7	Diabetes interferes with or prevent one from doing your normal daily activities	20	55	22	20.6	56.7	22.7	O
8	Use of sugars or sweet foods	28	16	53	28.9	16.5	54.6	N
9	Use artificial sweeteners	20	28	59	20.6	18.6	60.8	N
10	drink low-calorie soft drinks	12	51	34	12.4	52.6	35.0	O
11	Drink low-fat or skimmed dairy products	22	52	23	22.7	53.6	23.7	O

Data in Table 3, all 10 items had mean values ranging from 3.05 to 3.35. The values were within 2.50 - 3.49, hence, the factors that

influence food selection and consumption practices of diabetic patients in Nsukka Metropolis were all accepted.

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Factors that Influence Food Selection and Consumption Practices of Diabetic Patients in Nsukka Metropolis

S/N	Item	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Difficulty in avoiding favorite foods and having cravings for unhealthy foods	3.17	0.52	A
2	Economy reduces the options of what to eat	3.27	0.44	A
3	Difficulty in adapting from my regular meal schedule to diabetic diet makes it difficult	3.25	0.50	A
4	Continuous need to be conscious with food eaten makes managing diabetes a complicated issue	3.07	0.54	A
5	Inadequate restaurants that serve healthy food for diabetics reduces the options of foods available to diabetic patients	3.11	0.58	A
6	Numerous obligations at work reduces time to plan and follow healthy diet	3.06	0.59	A
7	Inadequate information on what to eat makes it difficult on the available diabetic food options	3.18	0.65	A
8	Over dependence on loved ones to provide healthy meal plans makes selection of foods complicated	3.05	0.67	A
9	Lack of varieties of foods to select from makes diabetic patients tired of the restriction	3.35	0.63	A
10	Inadequate support groups needed to strengthen resolved not to eat certain foods	3.24	0.61	A

Discussion of findings

The findings of the study on foods mostly selected for consumption by diabetic patients in Nsukka metropolis revealed that the commonly selected foods for consumption by the patients in the area were in line with Obayendo (2011) who found out that the diabetic patients take less of animal proteins like meat and fish in the morning, but the case is different in the afternoon (lunch) and night (dinner) where they took more of these animal proteins. Savoca and Miller (2011) found out that diabetic patients knew that eating foods high in carbohydrates increases blood glucose levels.

The findings of the study on food consumption practices of diabetic patients in Nsukka metropolis in line with Al-Daghri, (2011) who found out that the food consumption practices of diabetic patients include number of regular meals eaten in a day, and the composition of such meals as well as the extent to which diabetic patients comply with doctors' visits.

The findings of the study on factors that influence food selection and consumption practices of diabetic patients in Nsukka

Metropolis revealed that all the factors studied influence food selection practices of diabetics in the study area are in line with Travis, (1997) who found out that food selection habits of diabetic patients include difficulty in avoiding favorite foods and selecting healthful alternatives as well as managing their weight. Hunt, Pugh and Valenzuela, (2018) found that the factors that influence dietary habits of diabetic patients are difficulty in departing from their typical meal schedule, and eating restraint, travel, holidays, family events, and dining out challenged diabetic patients' efforts to follow a recommended meal plan. Dietary management is not an option for diabetics, a clearly defined dietary plan must be strictly adhered to promote general wellbeing.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Diabetes is a serious health condition that kills easily if not managed, it is important that diabetic patients adhere as to the strategies for improving food selection and consumption habit. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that:

1. Awareness should be created by hospitals and health personnel for diabetic patients on the right foods to eat, recommended foods does not have to be necessarily expensive, such that poor or average economic class families can afford such foods.
2. Family members should provide social support to Diabetic patients especially in the selection and preparation practices. A greater understanding is required in appreciating the need for diabetics to eat differently from other family members.
3. Diabetics should adhere to those factors that will promote healthy food consumption practices and avoid negative effect on their feeding which will consequently affect their health adversely.
4. Home Economists should develop an affordable diabetic diet across all the socio- economic levels

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